

VARIANTS OF THE MINIMUM ERROR THRESHOLDING METHOD FOR IMAGE SEGMENTATION

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Abstract: Image segmentation is an important problem because it enables meaningful partitioning of an image and extraction of relevant structures and features, facilitating further processing and decision-making. Various approaches have been proposed to address this problem, with one of the simplest and most commonly used being segmentation based on thresholding. This research relies on the classic and well-known Minimum Error Thresholding (MET) method, specifically employing a simple idea of linearly combining the MET method with its median-based extension, creating three modifications of MET method in order to improve thresholding results in terms of quality coefficients such as Mean Square Error (MSE) and Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM). Several experiments on some standard gray-level images have demonstrated that the proposed modifications improve segmentation performance, as confirmed by MSE and SSIM indices.

Keywords: Image segmentation, image thresholding, minimum error thresholding (MET) method, median-based methods.

1. INTRODUCTION

Image segmentation is one of the most important problems in image analysis since it is a required preprocessing step for computer vision tasks such as feature extraction and object recognition. Good segmentation enables precise introspection of specific regions within an image and enhances algorithm performance by reducing the amount of data to be processed.

A numerous techniques have been developed for image segmentation. Some of the most commonly used methods are traditional approaches such as threshold-based, edge-based, clustering-based, graph-based, and region-based methods. In addition, more recent and advanced techniques have been developed, including deep learning-based methods (e.g., U-Net, DeepLab), level set methods, and superpixel-based approaches (see, for example, Brar et al., 2025; Minaee et al., 2021). Although these techniques have become dominant, thresholding remains popular due to its simplicity and effectiveness and is often incorporated into more complex algorithms (Castiglione et al., 2025; Harrak et al., 2025; S. W. Kim et al., 2025).

Threshold methods were initially created to convert grayscale images into binary ones, aiming to identify background and foreground (object) regions. This is accomplished by setting a threshold value that assigns each pixel to one of two segments depending on its intensity. A single threshold value defines binary thresholding, while two or more define multilevel thresholding. Although simple and fast, these methods often perform poorly on noisy, low-contrast, or unevenly illuminated images.

The primary focus of many studies is to find optimal threshold values that accurately separate images into segments. The best-known method is the Otsu method (Otsu et al., 1975), followed by Kapur's (Kapur et al., 1985), Tsallis entropy-based (De Albuquerque et al., 2004), minimum cross entropy (Li & C. Lee, 1993), and Kittler and Illingworth's minimum error thresholding (MET) (Kittler & Illingworth, 1986). As the number of thresholds increases, computational time grows, so many hybrid variants have been proposed by combining these methods with optimization techniques such as nature-inspired algorithms (Abd El Aziz et al., 2017; Agrawal et al., 2013; Hancer, 2020; Horng, 2011; Houssein et al., 2021).

It is difficult to declare one thresholding method as universally best since performance depends on image properties and application. However, Sezgin and Sankur (2004) ranked the MET method as the best among those developed up to that point. Considering that MET is still used in its basic form in recent studies (Harrak et al., 2025; S. W. Kim et al., 2025), this paper focuses on MET and explores ways to enhance its

performance. Section 2 recalls the MET method and its median-based modification, Section 3 introduces three new variants, Section 4 presents experimental results and comparisons, and the final section contains concluding remarks.

2. THE MET METHOD AND ITS MEDIAN-BASED MODIFICATION

Suppose that a given gray-level image contains N pixels, and each pixel is represented by its intensity x_j , $j = 1, \dots, N$, where 0 and T are the smallest and the largest possible intensities, respectively ($T = 255$ for an 8-bit gray-level image). The associated histogram can be created by counting the number of pixels at each intensity level and plot these counts on a graph.

Let f_i denote the frequency of occurrence of level i in the image, and $p_i = f_i/N$ denote the probability of occurrence of level i . It is clear that

$$\sum_{i=0}^T f_i = N \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{i=0}^T p_i = 1. \quad (1)$$

Binary thresholding methods generate a threshold value t that splits the set of pixels into two classes $C_1(t)$ and $C_2(t)$ such that $C_1(t) = \{j \mid 0 \leq x_j \leq t, 1 \leq j \leq N\}$ and $C_2(t) = \{j \mid t < x_j \leq T, 1 \leq j \leq N\}$.

The MET method selects an optimal threshold value t^* that minimizes the objective function

$$J(t) = \omega_1(t) \cdot \log \frac{\sigma_1(t)}{\omega_1(t)} + \omega_2(t) \cdot \log \frac{\sigma_2(t)}{\omega_2(t)} \quad (2)$$

where $\omega_1(t)$ and $\omega_2(t)$ denote cumulative probabilities, while $\sigma_1(t)$ and $\sigma_2(t)$ are variances of the classes $C_1(t)$ and $C_2(t)$, which means that

$$\omega_1(t) = \sum_{i=0}^t p_i, \quad \omega_2(t) = \sum_{i=t+1}^T p_i = 1 - \omega_1(t), \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_1^2(t) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^t f_i (i - \mu_1(t))^2}{\sum_{i=0}^t f_i} = \frac{1}{\omega_1(t)} \sum_{i=0}^t p_i (i - \mu_1(t))^2, \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_2^2(t) = \frac{\sum_{i=t+1}^T f_i (i - \mu_2(t))^2}{\sum_{i=t+1}^T f_i} = \frac{1}{\omega_2(t)} \sum_{i=t+1}^T p_i (i - \mu_2(t))^2, \quad (5)$$

where $\mu_1(t)$ and $\mu_2(t)$ are the means of $C_1(t)$ and $C_2(t)$, i.e.

$$\mu_1(t) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^t f_i \cdot i}{\sum_{i=0}^t f_i} = \frac{1}{\omega_1(t)} \sum_{i=0}^t p_i \cdot i, \quad (6)$$

$$\mu_2(t) = \frac{\sum_{i=t+1}^T f_i \cdot i}{\sum_{i=t+1}^T f_i} = \frac{1}{\omega_2(t)} \sum_{i=t+1}^T p_i \cdot i. \quad (7)$$

Kurita et al. showed in [1] that the MET method can be derived from maximisation of log-likelihoods based on mixtures of Gaussian distributions.

In the case of multi-level thresholding, the MET method can be adapted to find certain number of classes. For example, if the number of classes is $K > 2$, then the aim of every method is to find $K - 1$ thresholding values $t = (t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{k-1})$ for defining C_1, C_2, \dots, C_K . Therefore, the objective function (2) can be rewritten and the appropriate optimization problem can be viewed as

$$t^* = \underset{t}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{k=1}^K \left\{ \omega_k(t) \log \frac{\sigma_k(t)}{\omega_k(t)} \right\} \quad (8)$$

Xue and Titterton proposed in [2] an alternative option, namely a modified MET method, which uses the median for location parameters instead of the means defined by (6) and (7). Analogously to the MET method, they presented a similar theoretical median-based approach using the mixtures of Laplace instead of Gaussian distribution. Accordingly, when the median is used instead of the mean, equations (4) and (5) for dispersion parameters are typically not used; instead, the mean absolute deviation from the median (MAD) is employed. Hence, in the case of the binary thresholding, MAD values are given by

$$\operatorname{MAD}_1(t) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^t f_i |i - m_1(t)|}{\sum_{i=0}^t f_i} = \frac{1}{\omega_1(t)} \sum_{i=0}^t p_i |i - m_1(t)|, \quad (9)$$

$$\operatorname{MAD}_2(t) = \frac{\sum_{i=t+1}^T f_i |i - m_2(t)|}{\sum_{i=t+1}^T f_i} = \frac{1}{\omega_2(t)} \sum_{i=t+1}^T p_i |i - m_2(t)|, \quad (10)$$

where $m_1(t)$ and $m_2(t)$ are the sample medians of $C_1(t)$ and $C_2(t)$. Therefore, the median-based MET method (denoted by medMET) gets the following form

$$t^* = \underset{t}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left(\omega_1(t) \log \frac{\operatorname{MAD}_1(t)}{\omega_1(t)} + \omega_2(t) \log \frac{\operatorname{MAD}_2(t)}{\omega_2(t)} \right), \quad (11)$$

The corresponding multi-level thresholding median-based MET variant is then

$$t^* = \underset{t}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{k=1}^K \left\{ \omega_k(t) \log \frac{\operatorname{MAD}_k(t)}{\omega_k(t)} \right\} \quad (12)$$

The motivation for introducing the median variant of the MET method was its better performance when the distributions of the classes C_k were skew or heavy-tailed. In such cases, it has been shown that the median is more robust location estimator than the mean, so then the median-based modification of the MET method is more suitable for the thresholds determination.

For instance, by applying the three-level thresholding MET and the modified median-based MET method on the 256×256 grey-level image given as Fig. 1, according to the results displayed in the associated histogram (Fig. 1), median-based MET method acts better than MET. Namely, for $K = 3$, the optimization rules given by (8) and (12) select the following threshold values: $t^* = (t_1^*, t_2^*) = (7, 23)$ for MET method and $t^* = (t_1^*, t_2^*) = (27, 119)$ for medMET, and these threshold values are displayed within histogram as dashed lines and dotted lines, respectively. Obviously, the histogram has three peaks and the MET thresholds lie close to the same valley, while medMET thresholds are better distributed between three peaks (medMET finds the valleys between the peaks) which indicate better separation of classes.

3. NEW VARIANTS OF MET-TYPE THRESHODLING METHODS

In this section, three new modified versions of the MET method are introduced. Actually, the new variants are combinations of the MET and medMET methods, aiming to preserve the good properties identified in Sezgin and Sankur (2004) and Xue and Titterington (2011) while potentially improving the performance of the initial approaches. All three variants are based on the arithmetic means of the components of the classical MET (2) and its median modification (11). In each of the three cases, the main idea is to take both the mean and the median into consideration simultaneously.

The first variant (denoted by METvar1) is a simple arithmetic mean of the objective functions (1) and (7)

$$t^* = \underset{t}{\operatorname{argmin}} \left(\frac{1}{2} \left[\omega_1(t) \log \frac{\sigma_1(t)}{\omega_1(t)} + \omega_2(t) \log \frac{\sigma_2(t)}{\omega_2(t)} \right] + \frac{1}{2} \left[\omega_1(t) \log \frac{\operatorname{MAD}_1(t)}{\omega_1(t)} + \omega_2(t) \log \frac{\operatorname{MAD}_2(t)}{\omega_2(t)} \right] \right). \quad (13)$$

Note that the objective function can be rewritten as

$$J(t) = \omega_1(t) \log \frac{\sqrt{\sigma_1(t) \operatorname{MAD}_1(t)}}{\omega_1(t)} + \omega_2(t) \log \frac{\sqrt{\sigma_2(t) \operatorname{MAD}_2(t)}}{\omega_2(t)} \quad (14)$$

where essentially the numerator represents the geometric mean of the standard deviation and the mean absolute deviation from the median.

If the arithmetic mean is used instead, we get another method (METver2) and the corresponding objective function

$$J(t) = \omega_1(t) \log \frac{s_1(t)}{\omega_1(t)} + \omega_2(t) \log \frac{s_2(t)}{\omega_2(t)} \quad (15)$$

where $s_1(t) = 0.5(\sigma_1(t) + \operatorname{MAD}_1(t))$ and $s_2(t) = 0.5(\sigma_2(t) + \operatorname{MAD}_2(t))$.

The third version METver3 relies on the basic mean value with the arithmetic mean and the median substituted in $\operatorname{MAD}_1(t)$ and $\operatorname{MAD}_2(t)$. Hence, the objective function has a form

$$J(t) = \omega_1(t) \log \frac{\operatorname{MAD}_{\operatorname{mod}_1}(t)}{\omega_1(t)} + \omega_2(t) \log \frac{\operatorname{MAD}_{\operatorname{mod}_2}(t)}{\omega_2(t)}, \quad (16)$$

where $\operatorname{MAD}_{\operatorname{mod}_1}(t)$ and $\operatorname{MAD}_{\operatorname{mod}_2}(t)$ are the values calculated using modified $\operatorname{MAD}(t)$ expressions such that

$$\operatorname{MAD}_{\operatorname{mod}_1}(t) = \frac{1}{\omega_1(t)} \sum_{i=0}^t p_i |i - r_1(t)| \quad \text{and} \quad \operatorname{MAD}_{\operatorname{mod}_2}(t) = \frac{1}{\omega_2(t)} \sum_{i=t+1}^T p_i |i - r_2(t)|, \quad (17)$$

for $r_1(t)$ and $r_2(t)$ given by $r_1(t) = 0.5 \cdot (\mu_1(t) + m_1(t))$ and $r_2(t) = 0.5 \cdot (\mu_2(t) + m_2(t))$.

Presented formulas (9), (10) and (11) are designed for determining a single threshold, and they also have extended analogous versions for multi-level thresholding as follows

$$t^* = \underset{t}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{k=1}^K \left\{ \omega_k(t) \log \frac{\sqrt{\sigma_k \operatorname{MAD}_k(t)}}{\omega_k(t)} \right\}, \quad t^* = \underset{t}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{k=1}^K \left\{ \omega_k(t) \log \frac{\operatorname{MAD}_k(t)}{\omega_k(t)} \right\} \text{ and} \\ t^* = \underset{t}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{k=1}^K \left\{ \omega_k(t) \log \frac{\operatorname{MAD}_k(t)}{\omega_k(t)} \right\} \quad (18)$$

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND COMPARISON

To illustrate the performance of the new variants of the MET method, three additional standard test gray-style 256×256 images are employed. These images are presented in Figures 1 (on the right) and 2 along with their associated histograms.

Despite the fact that it is difficult to designate any of the existing methods as the best due to the effectiveness of thresholding depends on the segmentation purposes, there are several commonly used thresholding quality indices for comparing methods. Hence, to evaluate the performance of the described methods and the segmentation accuracy of the experimental results, this research relies on two measures.

The first one is the Mean Square Error (MSE) , given by

$$MSE = \frac{1}{m \cdot n} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n (I(i, j) - S(i, j))^2, \quad (19)$$

where m and n represent the image dimensions, $I(i, j)$ and $S(i, j)$ are the intensities of pixel (i, j) in the original and segmented image, respectively. Lower MSE values indicate better segmentation results. Note that similar quality index PSNR (Peak Signal to Noise Ratio) can be derived from MSE since $PSNR = 20 \log_{10}(255/\sqrt{MSE})$.

Figure 1: Left two - Image *Girlface* and its histogram; Right two - Image *Peppers* and its histogram

Figure 2: Left two - Image *Polymersomes* and its histogram; Right two - Image *Crowd* and its histogram

Figure 3: Examples of the segmented *Polymersomes* image using three-level thresholding methods (from left to right: MET, medMET, METver1, METver3)

Another quality measure is the Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) , which quantifies the similarity between the original and segmented images in the following way:

$$SSIM(I, S) = \frac{(2\mu_I\mu_S+c_1)(2\sigma_{I,S}+c_2)}{(\mu_I^2+\mu_S^2+c_1)(\sigma_I^2+\sigma_S^2+c_2)}. \quad (20)$$

Here, μ_I and μ_S are the mean intensities of the original and segmented images, σ_I and σ_S are the standard deviations, while $\sigma_{I,S}$ denotes the covariance between I and S , and c_1 and c_2 are constants to stabilize the

division when the denominator is weak (the constants are commonly set to $c_1 = 0.0065025$ and $c_2 = 0.0585225$).

Table 1: Two-level thresholding - *Girlface, Peppers and Polymersomes*

Method	Girlface (two-level thresholding)			Peppers (two-level thresholding)			Polymersomes (two-level thresholding)		
	Threshold t^*	MSE	SSIM	Threshold t^*	MSE	SSIM	Threshold t^*	MSE	SSIM
<i>MET</i>	19	19935.35	0.96341	26	17432.58	0.96727	198	27146.20	0.94178
<i>medMET</i>	14	21243.92	0.96079	135	7505.38	0.98831	205	27691.48	0.94017
<i>METver1</i>	17	20416.79	0.96246	132	7458.78	0.98827	200	27284.13	0.94137
<i>METver2</i>	17	20416.79	0.96246	132	7458.78	0.98827	200	27284.13	0.94137
<i>METver3</i>	15	20953.42	0.96139	138	7584.59	0.98823	210	28083.60	0.93895

Table 2: Two-level thresholding - *Crowd*; Three-level thresholding - *Girlface and Peppers*

Method	Crowd (two-level thresholding)			Girlface (three-level thresholding)			Peppers (three-level thresholding)		
	Threshold t^*	MSE	SSIM	(t_1^*, t_2^*)	MSE	SSIM	(t_1^*, t_2^*)	MSE	SSIM
<i>MET</i>	91	6489.86	0.99349	(38,125)	4821.90	0.99137	(38,125)	4821.90	0.99137
<i>medMET</i>	96	6081.68	0.99364	(35,126)	4794.57	0.99139	(35,126)	4794.57	0.99139
<i>METver1</i>	92	6392.61	0.99354	(37,125)	4831.12	0.99135	(37,125)	4831.12	0.99135
<i>METver2</i>	92	6392.61	0.99354	(37,125)	4831.12	0.99135	(37,125)	4831.12	0.99135
<i>METver3</i>	92	6392.61	0.99354	(36,127)	4721.86	0.99155	(36,127)	4721.86	0.99155

Table 3: Three-level thresholding - *Polymersomes and Crowd*

Method	Polymersomes (three-level thresholding)			Crowd (three-level thresholding)		
	(t_1^*, t_2^*)	MSE	SSIM	(t_1^*, t_2^*)	MSE	SSIM
<i>MET</i>	(145,191)	2316.06	0.99569	(72,110)	4122.83	0.99520
<i>medMET</i>	(120,204)	1809.44	0.99648	(96,253)	3301.68	0.99385
<i>METver1</i>	(130,197)	1821.08	0.99651	(91,253)	3115.26	0.99446
<i>METver2</i>	(131,197)	1826.89	0.99650	(73,112)	4009.87	0.99532
<i>METver3</i>	(119,207)	1830.20	0.99639	(92,253)	3152.82	0.99433

Tables 1-3 illustrate the application of the described thresholding methods on the presented images. Specifically, the first four tables show the values of the MSE and SSIM coefficients for binary segmentation (two-level thresholding), while the next four tables present these values for multi-level segmentation (three-level thresholding). It is noticeable that the results vary depending on the image being analyzed and the number of threshold values being sought. For instance, for the binary thresholding applied on the girlface, the best MSE and SSIM values possesses MET method, while for the three-level case medMET provides better MSE and SSIM coefficients (as it could be expected according to the analysis of Fig. 1). Note that these coefficients are the best for METver3 in this case (Table 2 - section 2), as well as for the three-level thresholding in Table 2 and 3. METver1 and METver2 produce the same or very similar threshold values (and consequently MSE and SSIM indices) except in Table 3 section 2. Interestingly, in that case, the best MSE value corresponds to METver1, while the best SSIM value is associated with the METver2 method.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Many thresholding techniques, such as the MET method, are very suitable for image segmentation due to their simplicity, effectiveness, and ease of application. Through numerous research, these methods are improved and adapted to meet specific requirements or image characteristics. In this research, we have proposed three new methods for image thresholding, which are based on the MET and median MET approaches. The primary motivation for developing new methods is to combine the strengths of both approaches, resulting in new objective functions that carry information about both the means and medians of the classes. The presented experimental results suggest that the proposed methods could be valuable alternatives to the original methods.

However, to fully evaluate the usefulness and effectiveness of the presented methods, further research is necessary in the several areas: examining the effectiveness of the methods on a broader range of diverse images, analyzing their usability with noisy images, considering their application to color images, exploring potential improvements in computational efficiency, especially for multi-level thresholding, and potentially developing hybrid methods incorporating well-known techniques such as Otsu's and Kapur's methods.

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